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CHANGES IN INTRARENAL HEMODYNAMIC DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE OF VARIOUS GENESIS

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Abstract: The article examines changes in intrarenal hemodynamics in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) of various etiologies. The study analyzed renal arterial blood flow parameters — peak systolic velocity (V_s max), end-diastolic velocity (V_d), and resistive index (RI) — in patients with CKD caused by both non-diabetic and diabetic nephropathies.

According to the results, both groups showed a significant decrease in blood flow velocities and an increase in peripheral resistance. It was observed that hemodynamic disturbances develop in a similar pattern regardless of the etiology of nephropathy. The resistive index was proven to be an important diagnostic and prognostic indicator for assessing the degree of renal parenchymal damage and fibrosis.

The findings demonstrate that evaluating intrarenal hemodynamics in the early stages of CKD is of great importance for diagnosis and for selecting appropriate treatment strategies.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, hemodynamics, Doppler ultrasonography, resistive index, nephropathy, renal arteries, blood flow.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is one of the most urgent problems in modern medicine, with its prevalence steadily increasing from year to year. This condition is of great importance not only in nephrology but also in general therapeutic practice, as it significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases and disability.

In the diagnosis of CKD, glomerular filtration rate (GFR), albuminuria, biochemical tests, and instrumental examinations are widely used. However, these indicators do not always provide sufficiently accurate information in the early stages of the disease. Renal biopsy is an invasive method and cannot be applied in all cases.

From this perspective, the assessment of intrarenal hemodynamics is of considerable importance. Doppler ultrasonography (DUS) makes it possible to evaluate renal arterial blood flow parameters and represents a non-invasive and widely used diagnostic method.

Aim of the study

To assess intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) of various etiologies and to determine their clinical and diagnostic significance.

Current methods for diagnosing renal failure include the assessment of glomerular filtration rate, albuminuria/proteinuria, urine analysis, evaluation of electrolyte balance, renal biopsy, and ultrasound examination (US) to determine structural changes and kidney size. However, these parameters are not always sufficiently informative, particularly in the early stages of CKD, and do not adequately characterize the degree of renal damage and nephrosclerosis. Moreover, renal biopsy is not always feasible.

Therefore, there is a need to search for additional clinical and laboratory criteria for CKD diagnosis. In this context, the assessment of intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances is of particular importance. One of the imaging methods that allows evaluation of intrarenal hemodynamics is Doppler ultrasonography (DUS), which enables examination of renal blood vessels, assessment of blood flow, and determination of the resistive index.

To establish the diagnostic value of DUS in detecting CKD progression, clinical and laboratory parameters should be compared with resistive index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), peak systolic velocity (V_s max), and end-diastolic velocity (V_d) in the main and segmental renal arteries [1, 9, 12, 15; 18, 21].

Materials and Methods

A total of 140 participants treated in the Nephrology Department of the National Medical Center were included in the study. The participants were divided into the following groups:

Group 1: CKD patients with non-diabetic nephropathy (n = 75)
 Group 2: CKD patients with diabetic nephropathy (n = 45)
 Control group: apparently healthy individuals (n = 20)

In all participants, the following parameters were assessed using Doppler ultrasonography: 1. Peak systolic velocity (V_s max). 2. End-diastolic velocity (V_d). 3. Resistive index (RI)

Measurements were performed in the main, segmental, and interlobar renal arteries. Statistical analysis was carried out using methods of variation statistics.

The obtained results were analyzed to evaluate changes in intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in patients with CKD of different etiologies. In Group 1 (non-diabetic nephropathy), V_s max in the main renal arteries was 56.4 ± 3.74 cm/s. In both Group 1 and Group 2 (diabetic nephropathy), peak systolic velocity, end-diastolic velocity, and resistive index values in the main, segmental, and interlobar renal arteries were significantly decreased compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$). However, when comparing Group 1 and Group 2 with each other, the differences were statistically insignificant.

Table 1.1

Table 1.1. Pattern of changes in intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in the study groups

Parameters	Control	Group 1 (n	Group 2
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	group (n = 20)	= 75)	(n = 45)
<i>Main renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	87,8±0,91	* 56,4±3,74**	*** 55,3±3,27
V_d, cm/c	28,9±0,64	* 17,5±2,23**	*** 16,4±2,19
RI	0,64±0,01	0,68±0,01**	*** 0,70±0,01
<i>Segmental renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	58,4±0,82	* 42,1±1,44**	*** 40,9±1,47
V_d, cm/c	23,1±0,32	13,8±1,03**	*** 12,7±1,03
RI	0,61±0,02	0,67±0,01**	** 0,68±0,01
<i>Interlobar renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	37,8±0,88	* 26,1±0,87**	8*** 25,01±0,8
V_d, cm/c	15,4±0,60	9,7±0,63**	* 8,6±0,65*
RI	0,59±0,01	0,65±0,01**	** 0,66±0,01

Note: * – differences compared with the control group (* – $p < 0.05$, ** – $p < 0.01$, *** – $p < 0.001$); ^ – differences compared with Group 1 (^ – $p < 0.05$, ^^ – $p < 0.01$, ^^ – $p < 0.001$).

The significant increase in peak systolic velocity in both patient groups ($p < 0.001$) is a consequence of the nephroangiosclerotic process underlying the disease. This process is also reflected in the results of end-diastolic velocity, as shown in Figure 3.4. According to the literature, studying intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in the early stages of kidney damage not only helps to establish an accurate diagnosis but also provides a basis for selecting appropriate etiological and intensive treatment strategies [2,4,5,8–11]. Vasoconstriction of the renal arterioles leading to reduced renal blood flow is considered one of the key mechanisms in renal tissue injury and the development of renal failure.

The increase in peripheral vascular resistance and the reduction of renal parenchymal blood flow can be explained by spasm of the arterioles in the cortical layer. Damage to the proximal tubular cells is closely associated with pronounced hypoperfusion. Leakage of ultrafiltrate into the renal interstitium is characterized by tubular necrosis. As a result, vascular compression occurs, blood circulation deteriorates, and the main functional processes of the kidneys are impaired. The diagram based on resistive index (RI) values also demonstrated a significant increase in RI in both groups with CKD, regardless of etiology ($p < 0.01$).

Studying intrarenal hemodynamics in patients with CKD is considered highly important. Some authors recommend assessing the resistive index rather than cystatin C analysis for the early diagnosis of renal dysfunction, compared with humoral factors [50; pp. 78–82]. In addition, most studies are focused on differentiating renal and prerenal forms of renal failure associated with tubular necrosis. RI values become more pronounced in stage III of the disease. Therefore, in such cases, the main attention is directed not to blood flow velocity in renal vessels, but to the assessment of RI values [4; p. 112, 9; pp. 592–597]. According to a study conducted by T. A. Maryanova et al. (2023) in 233 pregnant women with CKD, it was reported that measuring peak systolic velocity in interlobar arteries provides relatively higher diagnostic value in this population [17; pp. 93–99].

It was also found that in patients there is a correlation between an increase in the resistive index (RI) of renal and intrarenal arterial blood flow and a decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Another important aspect of our study is that when comparing the reductions in V_s max and V_d , as well as the increase in RI values across different calibers of renal arteries, the differences were statistically insignificant. This suggests that intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in CKD patients develop through mechanisms that evolve independently of etiological factors. Thus, Doppler ultrasonography findings of renal arteries, particularly the RI, represent a reliable indicator for assessing the degree of renal fibrosis. Therefore, in clinical practice, it is advisable to use this parameter as an additional prognostic factor for predicting the progression of CKD [12; p. 13, 19; p. 25].

Doppler ultrasonography of the renal arteries was performed in all study groups at baseline and after six months of treatment. The dynamics of intrarenal hemodynamic changes in CKD patients of different etiologies under the influence of calcium dobesilate therapy demonstrated the following results. In the main renal arteries, V_s max in Group 1 (patients with CKD due to non-diabetic nephropathy) was 56.4 ± 3.74 cm/s at baseline. After six months, in Group 1A (patients receiving only standard therapy) it decreased insignificantly to 53.7 ± 1.87 cm/s, whereas in Group 1B (patients receiving standard therapy plus calcium dobesilate) it increased to 73.1 ± 4.11 cm/s. Statistical analysis showed that compared with baseline, V_s max decreased insignificantly in Group 1A, while in Group 1B it increased significantly ($p < 0.01$). Comparison of final values between groups revealed a significantly higher increase in Group 1B compared with Group 1A ($p < 0.001$). End-diastolic velocity (V_d) in Group 1 at baseline was 17.5 ± 2.23 cm/s. After six months, it decreased to 15.9 ± 1.92 cm/s in Group 1A, whereas in Group 1B it increased to 25.3 ± 1.95 cm/s. Statistical analysis demonstrated a non-significant decrease in Group 1A compared with baseline and a significant increase in Group 1B ($p < 0.01$). Intergroup comparison at the end of the study also showed a significantly higher V_d in Group 1B compared with Group 1A ($p < 0.001$). The resistive index (RI), calculated based on V_s max and V_d in the main renal arteries, was 0.68 ± 0.01 at baseline in Group 1. After treatment, it showed a non-significant increase to 0.69 ± 0.01 in Group 1A, while in Group 1B it decreased slightly to 0.65 ± 0.01 ($p < 0.05$). At the end of the

study, comparison between groups confirmed a significant reduction in RI in Group 1B compared with Group 1A ($p < 0.01$). (Table 5.5).

Table 1.2

Dynamics of intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in patients with non-diabetic chronic kidney disease under different treatment regimens

Parameters	Group 1 (n = 75) (NDE)	Group 1A (n = 35) (NDE + standard therapy)	Group 1B (n = 40) (NDE + D)
<i>Main renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	56,4±3,74	53,7±1,87	73,1±4,11 **^^^
V_d , cm/c	17,5±2,23	15,9±1,92	25,3±1,95 **^^^
RI	0,68±0,01	0,69±0,01	0,65±0,01 *^^
<i>Segmental renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	42,1±1,44	40,6±1,46	47,3±1,78 *^^
V_d , cm/c	13,8±1,03	13,4±1,22	16,9±1,15 *^
RI	0,67±0,01	0,68±0,01	0,64±0,01 *^^
<i>Interlobar renal artery</i>			
V_s max, cm/c	26,1±0,87	24,9±0,89	28,6±0,84 *^^
V_d , cm/c	9,7±0,63	8,8±0,68	11,0±0,54 ^
RI	0,65±0,01	0,66±0,01	0,63±0,01 *^

Note: * – differences compared with baseline values (* – $p < 0.05$, ** – $p < 0.01$, *** – $p < 0.001$); ^ – differences compared with Group A values (^ – $p < 0.05$, ^^ – $p < 0.01$, ^^ – $p < 0.001$).

In patients with CKD caused by diabetic nephropathy, intrarenal hemodynamic changes in the study groups demonstrated the following pattern. In the main renal arteries, V_s max in Group 2 at baseline was 55.3 ± 3.27 cm/s. After six months of treatment, it decreased to 52.6 ± 3.91 cm/s in Group 2A (standard therapy only), while it increased to 71.9 ± 4.02 cm/s in Group 2B (standard therapy combined with calcium dobesilate). Statistical analysis showed that, compared with baseline, V_s max decreased insignificantly in Group 2A, whereas it increased significantly in Group 2B ($p < 0.01$). Comparison of final values between groups demonstrated a significant increase in Group 2B compared with Group 2A ($p < 0.01$). End-diastolic velocity (V_d) in Group 2 at baseline was 16.4 ± 2.19 cm/s. After six months, it decreased to

14.8 ± 1.88 cm/s in Group 2A, whereas it increased to 24.2 ± 1.89 cm/s in Group 2B. Statistical analysis revealed a non-significant decrease in Group 2A and a significant increase in Group 2B ($p < 0.01$). Intergroup comparison at the end of the study also showed a significantly higher Vd in Group 2B compared with Group 2A ($p < 0.01$). The resistive index (RI), calculated from Vs max and Vd in the main renal arteries, was 0.70 ± 0.01 at baseline in Group 2. After treatment, it increased insignificantly to 0.72 ± 0.01 in Group 2A, while it decreased significantly to 0.66 ± 0.01 in Group 2B ($p < 0.01$). Final intergroup comparison showed a significant reduction in RI in Group 2B compared with Group 2A ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1.3).

Table 1.3

Dynamics of intrarenal hemodynamic disturbances in diabetic chronic kidney disease under different treatment regimens

Parameters	Group 2 (n = 45) (DE)	Group 2A (n = 20) (DE + standard therapy)	Group 2B (n = 25) (DE + D)
<i>Main renal artery</i>			
V _s max, cm/c	55,3±3,27	52,6±3,91	^^ 71,9±4,02**
V _d , cm/c	16,4±2,19	14,8±1,88	^^ 24,2±1,89**
RI	0,70±0,01	0,72±0,01	^^^ 0,66±0,01**
<i>Segmental renal artery</i>			
V _s max, cm/c	40,9±1,47	39,5±1,52	^ 46,2±1,86*^
V _d , cm/c	12,7±1,03	12,3±1,1	15,8±1,07*^
RI	0,68±0,01	0,69±0,01	0,66±0,01^
<i>Interlobar renal artery</i>			
V _s max, cm/c	25,01±0,88	23,8±0,87	^ 27,5±0,85*^
V _d , cm/c	8,6±0,65	7,8±0,67	9,9±0,59^
RI	0,66±0,01	0,67±0,01	0,64±0,01^

Note: * – differences compared with baseline values (* – $p < 0.05$, ** – $p < 0.01$, *** – $p < 0.001$); ^ – differences compared with Group A values (^ – $p < 0.05$, ^^ – $p < 0.01$, ^^ – $p < 0.001$).

Doppler ultrasound gradients of renal arteries of different calibers demonstrated a distinct pattern under various treatment regimens in the study groups. This reflected both the effectiveness of the applied therapeutic approaches and the degree of vascular sclerosis of the intrarenal vessels in patients with CKD of different etiologies.

Figure 1.1. Dynamics of changes in Vs max gradients under different treatment regimens in the study groups.

Analyzing the diagram based on these gradients shows that in Group B, where calcium dobesilate was used in addition to standard therapy, there was a significant increase in peak systolic velocity ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$) compared with Group A, which received only standard treatment, indicating an improvement in blood flow. This effect is particularly pronounced in the main and segmental renal arteries. Although changes in Vs max in the segmental and interlobar arteries were less significant compared with baseline, they were still markedly more pronounced in Group B than in Group A. This may be explained by the anti-aggregatory and angioprotective properties of calcium dobesilate. At the same time, the comparable values observed in both study groups suggest a relatively consistent hemodynamic response to the treatment across the groups, which is also noteworthy (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.2. Dynamics of changes in Vd gradients under different treatment regimens in the study groups.

End-diastolic velocity also showed a more favorable improvement in Group B compared with Group A, which is evidenced by a significant decrease in its values in the main renal arteries ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.001$). However, in the segmental and interlobar arteries, changes in Vd in the calcium dobesilate group were less statistically significant. Moreover, in the interlobar arteries of Group B, changes compared with baseline were not significant, indicating an increase in vascular resistance as the vessel diameter decreases. In general, the reduced statistical significance of hemodynamic parameters with decreasing vessel caliber in intrarenal circulation reflects the progressive increase in vascular resistance (Figure 1.2).

Overall, in our study, analysis of Vs max and Vd gradients under different treatment regimens further confirmed, during statistical processing, that the effectiveness of calcium dobesilate is comparable across the evaluated parameters.

Figure 1.3. Dynamics of changes in RI values under different treatment regimens in the study groups.

The resistive index demonstrated a distinct pattern across the study groups. As shown in Figure 5.8, at baseline the RI was higher in Group 2 (patients with diabetic nephropathy) compared with Group 1 (patients with non-diabetic nephropathy). Although a similar therapeutic effect was observed in the main renal arteries in both groups, this effect was not consistently reproduced in the segmental and interlobar arteries. In particular, after treatment, Group 2 showed a non-significant decrease in RI compared with baseline, and a less pronounced reduction compared with Group 1. This indicates differences in the effectiveness of the newly proposed drug in patients with diabetic CKD. This can be explained by the fact that,

in addition to atherosclerotic changes in the branches of the renal arteries and fibrosis of the renal parenchyma in non-diabetic nephropathy, diabetic patients also present with metabolic disorders that further aggravate vascular injury and increase intravascular resistance and pressure (Figure 5.8).

Results

1. According to the study results, in the main renal arteries, V_s max was 56.4 ± 3.74 cm/s in Group 1 and 55.3 ± 3.27 cm/s in Group 2, showing a significant decrease compared with the control group ($p < 0.001$).
2. The V_d parameter also demonstrated a significant difference, amounting to 17.5 ± 2.23 cm/s and 16.4 ± 2.19 cm/s, respectively.
3. The RI values were 0.68 ± 0.01 in Group 1 and 0.70 ± 0.01 in Group 2, indicating a significant increase.
4. A similar trend was observed in the segmental and interlobar renal arteries.

Conclusion

Thus, in our study, the effectiveness of calcium dobesilate added to standard therapy was evaluated through assessment of intrarenal hemodynamics in CKD patients with both non-diabetic and diabetic nephropathy. In the groups receiving calcium dobesilate for six months, a significant positive shift in V_s max and V_d gradients was observed in both etiological forms of CKD, confirming the therapeutic efficacy of the drug. In addition, the new agent demonstrated a more pronounced and statistically significant reduction in the resistive index in patients with non-diabetic CKD compared with those with diabetic nephropathy. Therefore, calcium dobesilate can be recommended not only for diabetic nephropathy but also for CKD of non-diabetic origin. Owing to its antiaggregant, antioxidant, and angioprotective properties, its use may contribute to slowing disease progression and reducing adverse outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Asadov R.Kh., Daminov B.T., Iskandarova Sh.T. The state of the hemodialysis service in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Scientific-Practical Journal "Pediatrics", No. 2, Tashkent, 2021, pp. 125–128.
2. Barnoev Kh.B., Sultonov N.N., Sabirov M.A. Chronic kidney disease: current issues of diagnosis and treatment. Uzbek Journal of Therapy, Tashkent, No. 1, 2020, pp. 147–153.
3. Barnoev Kh.B., Munavvarov B.A. Effectiveness of antiplatelet therapy on renal function in the pre-dialysis stage of chronic kidney disease. Uzbek Journal of Therapy, Tashkent, No. 1, 2021, pp. 113–117.
4. Batyushin M.M. Chronic kidney disease: current state of the problem. Rational Pharmacotherapy in Cardiology, 2020;16(6):938–947. DOI:10.20996/1819-6446-2020-11-06.

5. Berns A.S. et al. Assessment of hemostasis disorders using thrombodynamics in patients with chronic glomerulonephritis and nephrotic syndrome. *Therapeutic Archive*, 2022;94(6):738–742.
6. Bobkova I.N. et al. Chronic kidney disease: clinical guidelines. Moscow, 2021. https://rusnephrology.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/CKD_final
7. Bobrova L.A., Kozlovskaya N.L. Thromboembolic complications of nephrotic syndrome. *Therapeutic Archive*, 2020;92(6):105–116.
8. Bulanov A.Yu. Thromboelastography in modern clinical practice. Atlas. Moscow: N'yudamed, 2015.
9. Vlasova E.A. et al. Platelet function and morphology under anticoagulant therapy in patients with chronic kidney disease on hemodialysis. *Nephrology and Dialysis*, 2014;16(1):139–144.
10. Gazhonova V.E. et al. Prognostic value of renal resistive index in chronic kidney disease progression. *Therapeutic Archive*, 2015;87(6):29–33.
11. Gaipov A.E. et al. Assessment of renal hemodynamic reserve using Doppler ultrasonography and pharmacological test in CKD patients. *Clinical Medicine of Kazakhstan*, 2013;1(27):11–19.
12. Glazun L.O., Polukhina E.V. Ultrasound diagnosis of kidney diseases. Manual. Moscow, 2014, p. 296.
13. Gudkova T.V. Lipid peroxidation of platelets and vascular-platelet hemostasis in chronic pyelonephritis. *Nephrology*, 2005;3:70–74.
14. Dudko M.Yu. et al. Epidemiology of chronic kidney disease among residents of Moscow. *Clinical Nephrology*, 2019;3:37–41.
15. Esayan A.M. et al. Prevalence of chronic kidney disease in primary healthcare patients in Russia. *Nephrology*, 2021;13(3):6–16. DOI:10.18565/nephrology.2021.3.6-16
16. Zelenin K.N. et al. Platelet functional activity in stage 5D CKD. *Almanac of Clinical Medicine*, 2017;45(7):547–552. DOI:10.18786/2072-0505-2017-45-7-547-552
17. Clinical guidelines. Chronic kidney disease (CKD). Association of Nephrologists. *Nephrology*, 2021;25(5):10–82.
18. Kozlovskaya N.L. Low molecular weight heparins in prevention and treatment of thrombosis in CKD patients. *Effective Pharmacotherapy: Urology and Nephrology*, 2020.